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Deliverable D1.12

Report on the status of posting results

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Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	14 January 2026	Initial draft
V0.2	15 April 2026	Completion by Clinical sites
V1.0	19 May 2026	Final version submitted

¹ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

- R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
- DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

- PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
- SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

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List of Definitions

The definitions used in the deliverable are based on the AIDAVA Glossary [[ref](#)].

1. Executive Summary

Deliverable D1.12 reports on the status of AIDAVA's Open Science compliance as of Month 41 (January 2026), documenting how the consortium has deposited, described and made accessible its scientific publications, research datasets and other project outputs in accordance with Horizon Europe Open Access obligations and FAIR principles. A final update on these activities will be included in *D6.11 Update of Report on dissemination and communication activities 2* due in Month 48.

Scientific publications. The consortium has significantly exceeded its contractual KPI of 15 peer-reviewed publications: as of M41, AIDAVA researchers have produced 25 peer-reviewed publications and 8 preprints, with 24 papers indexed in Scopus and 14 in PubMed Central. Cumulative citations exceed 1,000 in Google Scholar (613 in Scopus), and the project h-index has risen from 6 at M36 to 8 at M41. All public deliverables (23 in total) are deposited on Zenodo and mirrored on OpenAIRE, ensuring long-term traceability and broad visibility.

Research data. AIDAVA applies the principle of "as open as possible, as close as necessary" to its two categories of research data. Pseudonymised and annotated clinical text corpora in Dutch (MUMC+), German (MUG) and Estonian (NEMC) — used for NLP model training — are managed under strict data transfer agreements and will be deleted or archived in de-identified label-only form at project end. Fully identifiable patient data (PHKGs, FHIR IPS, SMART scores) remain within the secure infrastructure of each clinical site in full compliance with GDPR, ethics committee approvals, and institutional governance; they have not left the hospital environment.

Dissemination of other results. Beyond publications, AIDAVA has disseminated results through 15 conferences and symposia, 2 patient consultant workshops (including the February 2025 Brussels event co-hosted with EHN), 2 SULO co-creation workshops, and through public GitHub repositories for the AIDAVA Reference Ontology and SULO codebase. Video outputs are hosted on the AIDAVA YouTube channel and Website

Compliance status. The consortium has established a shared publication strategy governing authorship, acknowledgements and repository submission workflows, enabling systematic tracking via tools such as Harzing's Publish or Perish. Open Science compliance is monitored through WP6 and aligned with the project's Data Management Plan and Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDEC).

2. Introduction and Open Science Strategy

The AIDAVA project (Grant Agreement No. 101057062) is implemented under the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions (RIA) framework and is therefore subject to the European Commission's requirements on Open Science, Open Access and responsible Research Data Management, as defined in the Grant Agreement and related Horizon Europe rules. In line with these obligations, AIDAVA has adopted a comprehensive Open Science strategy that ensures transparency, accessibility and long-term reuse of its scientific outputs, while fully respecting ethical, legal and data protection constraints.

AIDAVA develops and validates an AI-powered virtual assistant for the curation and publishing of heterogeneous personal health data. This involves complex technical results, software components, ontologies, scientific publications and research data. Given the sensitive nature of health-related data and the project's strong emphasis on GDPR compliance and ethics, Open Science within AIDAVA is implemented according to the principle of "**as open as possible, as closed as necessary.**" This principle is consistently applied across all work packages and results.

The project's Open Science approach is anchored in:

- Mandatory **Open Access to peer-reviewed scientific publications;**
- Structured **Research Data Management**, as defined in the Data Management Plan
- Use of **trusted repositories** and persistent identifiers to ensure traceability and long-term availability;
- Compliance with **FAIR principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable);
- Clear governance processes addressing **IPR, ethics, data protection and security** when accessing patient related data

This deliverable provides evidence of AIDAVA's compliance with these Open Science obligations. It documents how scientific publications, datasets and other project results are deposited, described and made accessible through appropriate repositories, as well as how metadata requirements defined in the Grant Agreement are fulfilled.

Open Science Strategy.

AIDAVA's Open Science strategy is defined and continuously refined through WP6 (Innovation Management: Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Sustainability), the Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDEC) and the Data Management Plan (DMP). It is implemented in close coordination with the project's legal, ethical and data protection frameworks.

Open Access to Scientific Publications

All peer-reviewed scientific publications resulting from AIDAVA are made openly accessible, while publications are deposited without undue delay and include complete, machine-readable metadata clearly referencing the project title, acronym (AIDAVA) and Grant Agreement number (101057062). Where publisher embargoes apply, these are respected in line with Horizon Europe rules, while ensuring eventual open accessibility.

Research Data Management and FAIR Data

AIDAVA applies structured research data management practices across the project lifecycle. Research outputs such as datasets, software artefacts, ontologies and documentation are assessed individually to determine the appropriate level of openness. Whenever data can be shared, it is deposited in

trusted repositories (see Section 5), metadata and clear licensing conditions. The FAIR principles guided the whole project, with particular emphasis on interoperability and reusability, which reflects the project's core objectives in data curation and standardisation.

Handling of Sensitive and Restricted Data

Due to the involvement of personal and health-related data, identifiable clinical data generated or processed within AIDAVA is not publicly shared. Such data remains securely stored within local hospital infrastructures or controlled environments, in full compliance with GDPR, ethics approvals and institutional governance requirements. For these cases, transparency is ensured through detailed metadata and clear justifications for restricted access, as foreseen under Horizon Europe Open Science rules.

Repositories and Persistent Identifiers

AIDAVA uses trusted, widely recognised repositories (such as Zenodo and institutional repositories) to host publications, datasets, software and other research outputs. These repositories support long-term preservation, versioning, and citation through persistent identifiers. Where relevant, software and technical artefacts are also linked to version-controlled platforms (e.g. GitHub), with archival releases deposited in repositories to ensure reproducibility.

Personal identifiable data are stored locally within the hospital's secure environment.

Quality Assurance and Compliance Monitoring

The consortium has established internal procedures to ensure that all deposited outputs (deliverables or papers) meet Horizon Europe Open Science requirements. This includes verification of metadata completeness, correct attribution of EU funding and consistency with the Grant Agreement. Progress on Open Science compliance is regularly monitored and reported through internal reporting mechanisms and dedicated dissemination deliverables.

3. Repository Infrastructure

3.1. Scientific Publications

The AIDAVA consortium has committed to securing open access to scientific publications related to the funding through trusted repositories. As partners prioritise dissemination of scientific outcomes at scientific conferences and in high-quality peer-reviewed journals, the respective papers can be accessed through the official journal/conference proceedings. They are all indexed via **Google Scholar** with a cumulative count of **over 1,000 citations**. Publication activity in the last couple of months of 2025 contributed to a higher h-index of 8 (see Figure 1 below), as compared to h-6 in M36 of the project.

Citation metrics ?	
Publication years:	2023-2025
Citation years:	3 (2023-2026)
Papers:	31
Citations:	1054
Cites/year:	351.33
Cites/paper:	34.00
Cites/author:	208.93
Papers/author:	7.57
Authors/paper:	4.52
h-index:	8
g-index:	31
hI,norm:	6
hI,annual:	2.00
hA-index:	6
Papers with ACC \geq 1,2,5,10,20:	16,12,8,5,3

Figure1. Results from Publish or Perish query for AIDAVA GA 101057062 in Google Scholar (2022-2025)

A strong indicator for the scientific impact of the research results in AIDAVA publications is their indexation in reputable scientific repositories like **Scopus** and **PubMed Central** – one of the largest collections of full-text publications in medicine. As of M41 of the project (January 2026), there are 24 publications indexed in Scopus and 14 publications indexed in PubMed Central (see Figure 2 below).

Figure 2. AIDAVA publications indexation in Scopus and PubMed Central

The AIDAVA publications indexed in **Scopus** have also achieved a good score of **613 citations** (see Figure 3 below). The *BMJ* paper “FUTURE-AI: international consensus guideline for trustworthy and deployable artificial intelligence in healthcare” contributed a fair share to the visibility of AIDAVA scientific results (346 citations in Google Scholar, 168 citations in Scopus).

Figure 3. AIDAVA publications citation overview on Scopus

AIDAVA's commitment to open science is further reinforced by the indexation of project-related papers in the world's largest open access database of academic research, **OpenAlex** (see Figure 4 below).

Figure 4. AIDAVA publications statistics on OpenAlex

3.2. Clinical data

Clinical data are stored within the 4 local hospitals contributing to the evaluation. Access to these data is further described in Section 5.

4. Status of Scientific Publications

The consortium has already exceeded the KPI set in the DoA, namely to produce at least 15 scientific publications on different topics in international journals and conferences. As of M41 of the project (January 2026), AIDAVA researchers have published **25 peer-reviewed publications** and **8 preprints**. The full list of publications is available in Appendix 1 List of publications.

In compliance with open science good practices, AIDAVA scientific papers are also indicated in the **OpenAIRE AIDAVA project website** (see Figure 5 below) along with the project deliverables. All deliverables with a Public dissemination level have been made openly available on the open general-purpose repository Zenodo. Since Zenodo was developed under the European OpenAIRE program, the materials uploaded there are also made available on the OpenAIRE platform, which further boosts the visibility of the project and its results. As of M41 (January 2026), **23 public deliverables** have been uploaded to Zenodo.

Figure 5. Excerpt of AIDAVA OpenAIRE project statistics

5. Status of Research Data

AIDAVA includes 2 types of data

- The annotated data set includes a set of pseudonymized/anonymized patients documents in 3 languages (German for MUG, Dutch for UM and Estonian for NEMC). These documents were annotated at the very start of the project (Task 4.3) to support training of the different NLP tools
- Fully identifiable data set coming from the MIDATA data intermediary and from the local hospital.

5.1.1 Annotated data sets

NEMC	
Description	<p>We used operative reports, radiology report texts, and patient discharge summaries related to cases involving surgical treatment, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy. The text corpus was annotated using codes corresponding to data elements in the breast cancer registry, including tumor location, surgical procedure, treatment modality, prognostic and predictive tumor markers, and disease stage. The annotation was not performed with maximal granularity and does not incorporate all possible SNOMED CT relationships. Instead, the annotation focused on a predefined set of information elements relevant to the registry and the objectives of the dataset. Consequently, not all potentially identifiable clinical concepts in the text were annotated. As a formal annotation guideline had not been finalized at the start of the annotation process, the dataset was annotated according to the best local expert judgment of the annotators. Therefore, the annotation scheme reflects a pragmatic and consensus-based approach aligned with the practical needs and intended use of the dataset.</p>
How to access them	<p>Several datasets have been created during the AIDAVA project:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) A dataset of annotated pseudonymized texts used to develop and train artificial intelligence models. This dataset of annotated pseudonymized texts will be deleted no later than the end of the project. 2) The annotations of the labeled texts will be archived in a form that does not contain the original texts at all. They will include only annotation labels and numerical references to the annotated text segments. For example, an annotation label with a terminological code indicating the start date of a chemotherapy treatment course, along with numerical references such as “start: 123, end: 133”. From the start and end positions of characters in the original text, it is not possible to indirectly identify anything other than the length of the annotated document. Along with the annotation files, documentation will be provided on how the original texts were retrieved from the PERH pseudonymized dataset. This information will be documented to enable the potential future retrieval of the original texts and retraining of AI models (not within the AIDAVA project and, of course, subject to obtaining the necessary ethical approvals and defining a new project). <p>Contact person/email (after project end):</p>

	Timo Piirsoo, timo.piirsoo@regionaalhaigla.ee
UM	
Short Description	Short description: AT UM diagnostic, lab and pathology anonymised reports were used from the cardiology department of MUMC. Also, radiotherapy related anonymised reports were used from the radiotherapy department of MUMC (MAASTRO clinic). The above mentioned reports were annotated by medical students based on the annotation guidelines authored by the MUG (Zenodo). The reports were written in Dutch and were hosted in a secure server hosted by MAASTRO (after the DTA between MUMC and MAASTRO).
How to access them	<p>For Maastricht University Medical Center+, data sharing follows a defined governance procedure. Specifically, access to data originating from Maastricht University requires completion of a formal data request process, including submission of the appropriate application form and the signing of a zero-hours contract. This procedure has already been implemented for collaborators from UM Institute of Data Science, Averbis GmbH, Ontotext AD, and KU Leuven. The shared data may be used exclusively during the project duration for the purpose of optimizing methods for representation, extraction, and standardization of clinical narrative content. After the end of the project, the data can be available upon request and the duration is set to the agreed time based on the IRB/METC approval (7 years after the end of the project)</p> <p>Contact person/email (after project end): Petros Kalendralis, petros.kalendralis@maastro.nl</p>
MUG	
Short Description	At MUG, anonymized document types of interest included pathology reports, radiotherapy treatment letters, and cardiological discharge summaries. They were annotated and curated according to the AIDAVA Annotation Guideline (Zenodo). In addition, the generation of a synthetic parallel corpus was organized (EN, ET, DE, NL), reflecting the document types in use from the different participating clinical sites. The narratives in German were fully semantically annotated by use of the Averbis pre-annotation pipeline, supporting the annotators in the task-intensive job.
How to access them	<p>The data can be provided to a designated responsible person, including the following institutions (KUL, Averbis GmbH, Ontotext AD, UM IDS), protected by a password and encrypted with AES256, as well as signed using SHA256 (https://box.medunigraz.at/). They may be used during the project duration for specific optimizations of the representation, extraction, and standardization of clinical narrative content. After the end of the project, the data must be deleted at the respective institutions. The annotated data sets can be repurposed for additional clinical NLP investigations by MUG in the future. The synthetically generated and annotated datasets are accessible from the project-specific Google Drive folder at the moment. Its access is not bound to the project duration.</p> <p>Contact person/email (after project end): Markus Kreuzthaler, markus.kreuzthaler@medunigraz.at</p>

5.1.2 Identifiable patient data sources

This includes several types of data

- GP, ePRO and medical devices data pooled through MIDATA collected by the patients in their MIDATA accounts. The terms of use of the web app regulate their use within AIDAVA: They are automatically copied to the AIDAVA software for ingestion by the patient in the AIDAVA software. The AIDAVA software incorporates them into the PHKG and derives an IPS. Within MIDATA, they are stored in encrypted patient accounts according to the MIDATA general terms and conditions and privacy policy and used according to the AIDAVA web app terms of use.. During the project these data were transmitted in a secure encrypted format to different hospitals following a data sharing agreement.
- Local hospital data sources. They were accessed and processed following full consent of the patient (based on ICF)
- Fully identifiable patient's personal health knowledge graph (PHKG) generated by AIDAVA during the curation and data quality enhancement process, as well as the International Patient Summary (in HL7 FHIR/EEHRxF format) and the cardio SMART score for CVD patients .
These data did not leave the hospital and were managed following the local hospital security and GDPR conditions.
These data are fully interoperable and reusable (under strict GDPR conditions)

NEMC	
Contact person in hospital	Aivi Karu, aivi.karu@regionaalhaigla.ee
Conditions under which data could be accessed	We are not allowed to use patient data in any form after the study is complete. We would need to apply for new permission to use the data, but if there is not a new project or a clear explanation for using the data, we cannot ask the ethics committee for permission.
MUG	
Contact person in hospital	datenschutz@medunigraz.at ethikkommission@medunigraz.at
Conditions under which data could be accessed	We are not allowed to use patient data in any form after the study is complete. We would need to apply for new permission to use the data, but if there is not a new project or a clear explanation for using the data, we cannot ask the ethics committee for permission.
UM/Maastro & MUMC	
Contact person in hospital	privacy@mumc.nl irb@maastro.nl
Conditions under which data could be accessed	Any request to access or process patient data must follow the procedures agreed upon with participants as outlined in the participant information sheet and applicable contracts. For protocol or documentation changes, a formal amendment must be submitted to the relevant ethics dossier (e.g., dossier 24-007); for cases not filed in the nWMO-portal, revised documents and a cover letter should be submitted via email.

	<p>Requests involving identifiable data (rather than pseudonymized data) require prior justification, including: the specific purpose of processing, whether additional participant consent is needed, how the data will be handled and stored going forward, and the basis for any deviations from standard pseudonymization procedures. These justifications must be reviewed and approved by the institution's privacy officer and legal team before data access is granted.</p>
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6. Dissemination of Other Results

In addition to scientific publications, AIDAVA partners have made scientific results visible through active participation in conferences and symposia targeted at the different stakeholder groups: healthcare providers, data stewards, regulators, health tech and the scientific community. A detailed account on dissemination activities can be found in section 2.2.2 of deliverable D6.7 and in section 2.3.3 of deliverable D6.10. Highlights include:

- **15 conferences/symposia** (3 out of which co-organised by AIDAVA consortium partners) for scientific exchange and network building with the research, business and policymaking communities
- **2 patient consultants workshops** – The main one was the AIDAVA and EHN-hosted patient consultants workshop held in Brussels on 26 February 2025, which discussed important topics such as patient perspectives on data quality scores and patient advocacy strategies for engaging policymakers. At the EHN Annual Workshop and General Assembly in Stockholm, Sweden (June 2025) our partner from DFP, Kristof Vanfraechem, introduced the AIDAVA approach in his talk “Co-designing the digital future of Europe’s healthcare with patients and their frontline HCPs: AIDAVA”.
- **1 poster presentation** for the SemTab’23 workshop at the International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC)
- **2 co-creation workshops** on the Simplified Upper-Level Ontology (SULO) with experts in ontology, health data standards and semantic interoperability.

AIDAVA researchers openly share their achievements in building the AIDAVA Reference Ontology and SULO through a **public GitHub repository**³ to benefit the wider research community.

The AIDAVA **YouTube channel**⁴ can be regarded as the public digital repository of video materials, targeted primarily at a broader audience to highlight the impact of AIDAVA outcomes.

³ <https://github.com/AIDAVA-DEV>

⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/@aidavaproject>

7. Quality Assurance and Validation

The consortium has established a publication strategy, detailing publication rules and guidelines on authorship and acknowledgements. Setting this up in a collaborative spirit has been essential for clarifying responsibilities and avoiding delays, disagreements and misunderstandings. This publication strategy covers all types of project publications (such as presentations, press releases, scientific papers, pre-prints, posters, abstracts, pre-registrations, and so on). This facilitates the follow-up of project publications. One of the key points in the publication strategy is the detailed instruction on how to include an acknowledgement to the AIDAVA project through the following three major references: project name, funding programme and Grant Agreement number (plus the Horizon Europe disclaimer).

Thanks to partners' diligence in correctly acknowledging the project, we can easily extract statistics about AIDAVA-related publications via a software tool like Harzing's Publish or Perish. It offers a handy way to search within the full text of publications indexed on Google Scholar by entering as a search term the project's name (AIDAVA) or the project's ID (GA number 101057062), since those should be included in the Acknowledgements section of each project-related publication.

Appendix 1. List of publications

Published peer-reviewed publications

	Publication
1	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Halilaj, Iva, Relinde IY Lieveise, Cary JG Oberije, Lizza EL Hendriks, Charlotte Billiet, Ines Joye, Brice van Eeckhout, Anke Wind, Anshu Ankolekar, and Philippe Lambin</p> <p>TITLE: Improving Patient Engagement in Phase 2 Clinical Trials with a Trial-specific Patient Decision Aid: Development and Usability Study (2025) J Med Internet Res 2025; 27:e71817 DOI: https://doi.org/10.2196/71817</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Journal of Medical Internet Research ISSN: 1438-8871 PUBMED ID: 40931488 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
2	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Khan H, Woodruff HC, Giraldo DL, Werthen-Brabants L, Mali SA, Amirrajab S, De Brouwer E, Popescu V, Van Wijmeersch B, Gerlach O, Sijbers J, Peeters LM and Lambin P</p> <p>TITLE: Leveraging Hand-Crafted Radiomics on Multicenter FLAIR MRI for Predicting Disability Progression in People with Multiple Sclerosis (2025) Frontiers in Neuroscience, 19:1610401 DOI: https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2025.1610401</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Frontiers in Neuroscience ISSN: 1662-453X DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
3	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Lambin, P., Woodruff, H.C., Mali, S.A. et al.</p> <p>TITLE: Radiomics Quality Score 2.0: towards radiomics readiness levels and clinical translation for personalized medicine (2025) Nature Reviews Clinical Oncology 22, 831–846 DOI: https://doi.org/10.1038/s41571-025-01067-1</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Nature Reviews Clinical Oncology ISSN: 1759-4782 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: No CITATIONS: Cited 12 times</p>
4	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: van Mierlo R, Liang W, Norak K, Kargl M, Maasik M, Bynens A-L, Plass M, Kreuzthaler M, Benedikt M, Hochstenbach L, van 't Hof A, Celebi R, Dekker A, de Zegher I and Kalendralis P and the AIDAVA consortium</p> <p>TITLE: An AI-powered data curation and publishing virtual assistant: usability and explainability/causability of, and patient interest in the first-generation prototype (2025) Frontiers in Digital Health 7:1629413</p>

	<p>DOI: https://doi.org/10.3389/fdgth.2025.1629413</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Frontiers in Digital Health ISSN: 2673-253X DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
5	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Declerck J, Kiliç ÖD, Emir Erol E, Mehryar S, Kalra D, de Zegher I, Celebi R TITLE: Assessing Data Quality in Heterogeneous Health Care Integration: Simulation Study of the AIDAVA Framework (2025) JMIR Med Inform 2025;13:e75275 DOI: https://doi.org/10.2196/75275</p> <p>PUBLISHER: JMIR Medical Informatics ISSN: 2291-9694 PUBMED ID: 41223409 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
6	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Sun, Wei; Li, Mingxiao; Sileo, Damien; Davis, Jesse J.; Moens, Marie Francine TITLE: Generating Explanations in Medical Question-Answering by Expectation Maximization Inference over Evidence (2025) ACM Transactions on Computing for Healthcare, 6 (2), art. no. 23, DOI: 10.1145/3712296 https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-105004401673&doi=10.1145%2F3712296&partnerID=40&md5=55fcdcae9a25524e804bc8ec2f3c1279 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001484840100003</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Association for Computing Machinery ISSN: 26911957, 26378051 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 0 times. Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 0 times WOS CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
7	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Widaatalla, Yousif ; Wolswijk, Tom ; Khan, Muhammad Danial ; Halilaj, Iva ; Mosterd, Klara ; Woodruff, Henry C. ; Lambin, Philippe TITLE: Radiomics in Dermatological Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT): Feature Repeatability, Reproducibility, and Integration into Diagnostic Models in a Prospective Study (2025) Cancers, 17 (5), art. no. 768. DOI: 10.3390/cancers17050768 https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-86000601084&doi=10.3390%2Fcancers17050768&partnerID=40&md5=faabcbe97c5ddc9d00ac4d4b86347c8b https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001442265500001</p>

	<p>PUBLISHER: Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI) ISSN: 20726694 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 0 times. Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 2 times. WOS CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
8	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Van Camp, Astrid ; Punter, Eva ; Houbrechts, Katrien ; Cockmartin, Lesley ; Prevos, Renate ; Marshall, Nicholas William ; Woodruff, Henry C. ; Lambin, Philippe ; Bosmans, Hilde T.C. TITLE: An automated toolbox for microcalcification cluster modeling for mammographic imaging (2025) Medical Physics, 52 (2), pp. 1335 - 1349. DOI: 10.1002/mp.17521 https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85209893647&doi=10.1002%2Fmp.17521&partnerID=40&md5=830abe3140f5d32e81b28c95a34bbea6 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001393215700001 https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11788264/</p> <p>PUBLISHER: John Wiley and Sons Ltd ISSN: 00942405, 24734209 ISBN: 9781622575909 CODEN: MPHYA PUBMED ID: 39569820 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 0 times. Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 2 times WOS CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
9	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Lekadir, Karim ; Frangi, Alejandro F. ; Porras, Antonio Reyes ; Glocker, Ben ; Cintas, Celia ; Langlotz, Curtis P.M.D. ; Weicken, Eva ; Asselbergs, Folkert W. ; Prior, Fred W. ; Collins, Gary S. TITLE: FUTURE-AI: International consensus guideline for trustworthy and deployable artificial intelligence in healthcare (2025) BMJ, art. no. e081554. DOI: 10.1136/bmj-2024-081554 https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85217663528&doi=10.1136%2Fbmj-2024-081554&partnerID=40&md5=f8a8f2c0337c411e1b9528f7ce0520c6 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001427239400009</p> <p>PUBLISHER: BMJ Publishing Group ISSN: 00071447, 09598146, 17561833 CODEN: BMJOA PUBMED ID: 39909534 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: aip OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 56 times.</p>

	<p>Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 346 times WOS CITATION: Cited 48 times</p>
10	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Laurent, Pierre Antoine ; André, Fabrice ; Bobard, Alexandre ; Deandreis, Désirée ; Demaria, Sandra ; Depil, Stéphane ; Eichmüller, Stefan B. ; Fernandez-Palomo, Cristian ; Foijer, Floris ; Galluzzi, Lorenzo TITLE: Pushing the boundaries of radiotherapy-immunotherapy combinations: highlights from the 7th immunorad conference (2025) OncoImmunology, 14 (1), art. no. 2432726. DOI: 10.1080/2162402X.2024.2432726 https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85212767581&doi=10.1080%2F2162402X.2024.2432726&partnerID=40&md5=a1142047981af85a6ece7d901d823128 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001381102400001</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Taylor and Francis Ltd. ISSN: 2162402X, 21624011 PUBMED ID: 39696783 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GOLD OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 3 times. Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 6 times WOS CITATION: Cited 2 times</p>
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13	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Van Camp, Astrid ; Woodruff, Henry C. ; Cockmartin, Lesley ; Marshall, Nicholas William ; Bosmans, Hilde T.C. ; Lambin, Philippe TITLE: Simulated image-specific microcalcification clusters and associated mass enhancement to enhance training of a deep learning model for cancer detection in contrast-enhanced mammography (2024) Proceedings of SPIE - The International Society for Optical Engineering, 13174, art. no. 1317404. DOI: 10.1117/12.3026879 https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85195387939&doi=10.1117%2F12.3026879&partnerID=40&md5=0a1792e924d04a355758b79d306abc12 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001239315300003</p> <p>PUBLISHER: SPIE SPONSORS: Barco, Inc., Beekley Medical, Clarix Imaging, CMR Molecular Imaging, Densitas Health, et al. CONFERENCE NAME: 17th International Workshop on Breast Imaging, IWBI 2024 CONFERENCE LOCATION: Chicago, IL, Rubenstein Forum on the University of Chicago Campus CONFERENCE CODE: 199943 ISSN: 0277786X, 1996756X ISBN: 9781510692657, 9781510690561, 9781510693302, 9781510692251, 9781510692275, 9781510693081, 9781510688728, 9781510688629, 9781510692671, 9781510693326 CODEN: PSISD DOCUMENT TYPE: Conference paper PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN FINAL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 0 times. Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 1 times WOS CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
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17	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Beuque, Manon P.L. ; Lobbes, Marc B.I. ; van Wijk, Yvonka ; Widaatalla, Yousif ; Primakov, Sergey P. ; Majer, Michael ; Balleyguier, Corinne S. ; Woodruff, Henry C. ; Lambin, Philippe</p> <p>TITLE: Combining Deep Learning and Handcrafted Radiomics for Classification of Suspicious Lesions on Contrast-enhanced Mammograms (2023) Radiology, 307 (5), art. no. e221843. DOI: 10.1148/radiol.221843 https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85163922659&doi=10.1148%2Fradiol.221843&partnerID=40&md5=11f33bde2ceb494dbac07a2e16d328a0 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001061457800008 https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37338353/</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Radiological Society of North America Inc. ISSN: 00338419, 15271315 CODEN: RADLA PUBMED ID: 37338353 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 44 times. Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 68 times WOS CITATION: Cited 38 times.</p>
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20	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Schulz, Stefan ; Del-Pinto, Warren ; Han, Lifeng ; Kreuzthaler, Markus ; Aghaei, Sareh ; Nenadic, Goran TITLE: Towards principles of ontology-based annotation of clinical narratives (2023) CEUR Workshop Proceedings, 3603, pp. 36 - 47. PID: https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3603/icbo2023_proceedings.pdf#page=51 https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85178585442&partnerID=40&md5=00f37d20b44ee07a2ff64d86ac809e06</p> <p>PUBLISHER: CEUR-WS SPONSORS: Alma Sirio-Libanes CONFERENCE NAME: 14th International Conference on Biomedical Ontologies, ICBO 2023 CONFERENCE LOCATION: Brasilia CONFERENCE CODE: 196075 ISSN: 16130073 ISBN: 9789666544899, 9788073780029, 9788024810256, 9789986342748, 9788073781712, 9782954494807, 9788024823911, 9789562361989, 8024810255, 807378002X DOCUMENT TYPE: Conference paper PUBLICATION STAGE: Final OPEN ACCESS: ALL OPEN ACCESS; GREEN ACCEPTED OPEN ACCESS; GREEN OPEN ACCESS SCOPUS CITATION: Cited 0 times. Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 4 times</p>
21	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Mali, Shruti Atul, Nastaran Mohammadian Rad, Henry C. Woodruff, Adrien Depeursinge, Vincent Andrearczyk, and Philippe Lambin TITLE: Harmonizing CT scanner acquisition variability in an anthropomorphic phantom: A comparative study of image-level and feature-level harmonization using GAN, ComBat, and their combination (2025) <i>PloS one</i> 20, no. 5: e0322365 DOI: https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0322365 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001488720800048</p> <p>PUBLISHER: <i>PloS one</i></p>

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23	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Uma, Kanimozhi, Sumam Francis, and Marie-Francine Moens TITLE: Masking language model mechanism with event-driven knowledge graphs for temporal relations extraction from clinical narratives (2023) <i>Complex Networks & Their Applications XII. COMPLEX NETWORKS 2023. Studies in Computational Intelligence, vol 1141. Springer, Cham, (pp. 162-174).</i> DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-53468-3_14 https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:001264435300014</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Springer, Cham CONFERENCE NAME: <i>International Conference on Complex Networks and Their Applications, COMPLEX NETWORKS 2023</i> CONFERENCE LOCATION: Menton, France ISBN: 978-3-031-53467-6 DOCUMENT TYPE: Article PUBLICATION STAGE: Final Google Scholar CITATION: Cited 1 times WOS CITATION: Cited 0 times</p>
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	WOS CITATION: Cited 0 times
25	<p>AUTHOR FULL NAMES: Philipp Daumke, Christian Haverkamp, Simone Heckmann, Marcus Kuper, Annett Müller, Frank Oemig, Uta Ripperger, Stefan Sabutsch, André Sander & Stefan Schulz</p> <p>TITLE: Kommunikationsfähigkeit und Interoperabilität von Gesundheitsdaten in einem vernetzten Gesundheitssystem. (2024) Health Data Management, pp 457–496 DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-43236-2_41</p> <p>PUBLISHER: Health Data Management DOCUMENT TYPE: Chapter in a Book PUBLICATION STAGE: Final</p>

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	Publication
1	<p>Sina Amirrajab, Zohaib Salahuddin, Sheng Kuang, Henry C. Woodruff, Philippe Lambin. "Radiology Report Conditional 3D CT Generation with Multi Encoder Latent diffusion Model." <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:2509.14780</i> (2025). https://arxiv.org/abs/2509.14780</p>
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3	<p>Salahuddin, Zohaib, Abdalla Ibrahim, Sheng Kuang, Yousif Widaatalla, Razvan L. Miclea, Oliver Morin, Spencer Behr et al. "Counterfactuals and Uncertainty-Based Explainable Paradigm for the Automated Detection and Segmentation of Renal Cysts in Computed Tomography Images: A Multi-Center Study." <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:2408.03789</i> (2024). https://arxiv.org/abs/2408.03789</p>
4	<p>Khan, Danial, Zohaib Salahuddin, Yumeng Zhang, Sheng Kuang, Shruti Atul Mali, Henry C. Woodruff, Sina Amirrajab et al. "Explainable Anatomy-Guided AI for Prostate MRI: Foundation Models and In Silico Clinical Trials for Virtual Biopsy-based Risk Assessment." <i>arXiv preprint arXiv:2505.17971</i> (2025). https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.17971</p>

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